

Synthetic Studies in the Indole Field. Part X. Synthesis of some Nitrotryptophans

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5-Methyl-7-nitro- and 7-methyl-5-nitrotryptophans and *N*-acetyl-5-methoxy-7-nitrotryptophan have been synthesised by the Gramine route. 5-Methyl-7-nitrotryptophan has also been synthesised by Warner and Moe's method.

Anderson¹ discovered that 5-methyltryptophan inhibited the growth of *Bact. coli* in very low concentration. Rydon² synthesised all the Bz-methyltryptophans and Fildes and Rydon³, who studied their action on the growth of *B. typhosum* 3390, found that the four Bz-methyltryptophans inhibited the growth in the order: 4 > 5 > 6 > 7. The growth-inhibitory properties of methyltryptophans have also been studied by others⁴⁻⁷. As the nitroindoles and nitrotryptophans would be of interest for study as bacterial inhibitors as compounds having a powerful electron-attracting group, 7-nitrotryptophan was synthesised by the present authors⁸. In continuation of our previous work on nitroindole derivatives of biological interest⁹⁻¹³, the syntheses of 5-methyl-7-nitro-, 7-methyl-5-nitro-, and *N*-acetyl-5-methoxy-7-nitro-tryptophans are described in the present communication.

All these tryptophans were synthesised by the Gramine route (Chart I). The substituted nitroindole (I) was subjected to the Mannich reaction with formaldehyde and diethylamine to furnish 3-diethylaminomethylnitroindole (II). This on reaction with ethyl acetamidomalonate in dry toluene in presence of catalytic amount of sodium hydroxide afforded ethyl α -acetamido- α -ethoxycarbonyl- β -(nitro-3-indolyl)propionate (III) which on further hydrolysis and decarboxylation afforded the corresponding tryptophan (V). 5-Methoxy-7-nitrotryptophan (Vc) could not be obtained from (IIIc) by employing the method described for (Va) (*vide infra*). Hence an alternative procedure¹⁴ was tried. The condensation product (IIIc) on heating under reflux with 10% sodium hydroxide

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solution yielded α -acetamido- α -carboxy- β -(5-methoxy-7-nitro-3-indolyl)propionic acid after acidification with hydrochloric acid. It was directly converted into *N*-acetyl-5-methoxy-7-nitrotryptophan (IVc) by heating under reflux with water. But deacetylation and isolation of the amino-acid could not be achieved even after repeated attempts with varying experimental conditions.

- (a) : $R_1 = \text{Me}$; $R_2 = \text{NO}_2$.
 (b) : $R_1 = \text{NO}_2$; $R_2 = \text{Me}$.
 (c) : $R_1 = \text{OMe}$; $R_2 = \text{NO}_2$.

5-Methyl-7-nitrotryptophan (Va) was also synthesised by Warner and Moe's method¹⁵. Acrolein was allowed to react with ethyl acetamidomalonate and the addition product¹⁵ reacted with 2-nitro-4-methylphenylhydrazine to provide γ -acetamido- $\gamma\gamma$ -diethoxycarbonyl *n*-butyraldehyde-2-nitro-4-methylphenylhydrazone (VI) which was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid to furnish ethyl α -acetamido- α -ethoxycarbonyl- β -(5-methyl-7-nitro-3-indolyl)propionate in good yield. It was identical with compound (IIIa) obtained by the Gramine route. This was subsequently converted into 5-methyl-7-nitrotryptophan (Va) according to the procedure followed earlier.

Our attempt to synthesise 4-nitro-7-methyltryptophan by the Gramine route was unsuccessful as 4-nitro-7-methylindole did not undergo the Mannich reaction with formaldehyde and diethylamine, probably due to steric reasons. Hence, the synthesis of the compound by Warner and Moe's method¹⁵ was attempted. γ -Acetamido- $\gamma\gamma$ -diethoxycarbonyl-*n*-butyraldehyde-2-methyl-5-nitrophenylhydrazone (VII) was obtained by the

reaction of 2-methyl-5-nitrophenylhydrazine with acrolein and ethyl acetamidomalonate. Attempts to cyclise (VII) with mild cyclising agents gave back the starting material, whereas cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid resulted in a dark coloured sticky mass from which no crystalline material could be isolated.

(VI) : $\text{R}_1 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_2 = \text{Me}$; $\text{R}_3 = \text{NO}_2$.

(VII) : $\text{R}_1 = \text{NO}_2$; $\text{R}_2 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_3 = \text{Me}$.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Nitro-7-methyl-, 5-nitro-7-methyl-, 5-methyl-7-nitro-, and 5-methoxy-7-nitroindoles were prepared from the corresponding nitrophenylhydrazones of ethyl pyruvate¹⁰. The various 3-diethylaminomethylnitroindoles were prepared as described earlier¹¹.

General Procedure for the Preparation of Ethyl α -Acetamido- α -ethoxycarbonyl- β -(nitro-3-indolyl)propionate (III).—A mixture of dry toluene (5 ml), powdered NaOH (0.1 g.), 3-diethylaminomethylnitroindole (II, 1 g.) and ethyl acetamidomalonate (1 g.) was heated under reflux in a slow current of nitrogen until the liberation of diethylamine had ceased. The mixture was cooled, the solid collected by filtration, and washed with a few ml of ice-cold water. The compound was then purified by crystallisation from ethanol.

The various compounds (III, a-c) with their physical properties and analytical data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Ethyl α -acetamido- α -ethoxycarbonyl- β -(nitro-3-indolyl)propionates (III).

No.	R ₁ .	R ₂ .	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Required.
IIIa	Me	NO ₂	217-18°	61%	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₇ N ₃	C: 56.52% H: 6.01 N: 10.58	56.29% 5.72 10.37
IIIb	NO ₂	Me	224-25°	77	„	C: 56.45 H: 5.92 N: 10.44	56.29 5.72 10.37
IIIc	OMe	NO ₂	191-92°	75	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₈ N ₃	C: 54.36 H: 5.87 N: 10.25	54.15 5.50 9.97

5-Methyl-7-nitrotryptophan (Va).—The condensation product (IIIa, 1 g.) was heated under reflux with a solution of NaOH (1 g.) in water (5 ml) and ethanol (10 ml) for 3 hr. The ethanol was removed under reduced pressure. To the residue, dissolved in water (5 ml), HCl (conc., 5 ml) was added and the mixture heated under reflux for 3 hr. The yellow solution containing a small amount of resinous material was filtered and to the clear filtrate a 2 *N*-NaOH solution was added dropwise till the solution was brought to pH 5-6, when a yellow solid separated. The mixture was kept overnight and the solid (0.55 g.) collected. This was dissolved in minimum amount of dilute alkali, decolorised with Norit, and the clear solution brought to pH 5-6 with dilute acetic acid. The mixture was left overnight in a refrigerator when a yellow solid separated. This was collected, washed with hot water, and dried; m.p. 260-61°. It gave a positive ninhydrin test. (Found: C, 55.04; H, 5.31; N, 15.52. $C_{12}H_{13}O_4N_3$ requires C, 54.75; H, 4.98; N, 15.96%.)

γ-Acetamido-γγ-diethoxycarbonyl-n-butyraldehyde-2-nitro-4-methylphenylhydrazone (VI).—Ethyl acetamidomalonate (10.9 g.), anhydrous ethanol (25 ml), and metallic sodium (0.05 g.) were cooled in an ice bath at 0° and mechanically stirred. Acrolein (3.2 g.) in the same solvent (5 ml) was added dropwise during 1 hr., the temperature of the reaction mixture being maintained at 3-7°. The stirring was continued for an hour more when a clear yellow solution resulted. The mixture was kept for 2 hr. at 3°; glacial acetic acid (1.5 ml) was added, followed by 2-nitro-4-methylphenylhydrazine¹⁶ (7.5 g.). The mixture was warmed to 50°, water (10 ml) added, and left overnight. More water was added to the flask and cooled in a freezing mixture when a reddish oil separated. It was extracted with ether and the extract dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent furnished a reddish thick oil (10 g.). This oil refusing to be crystallised was directly used for the next stage.

Ethyl α-Acetamido-α-ethoxycarbonyl-β-(5-methyl-7-nitro-3-indolyl) propionate (IIIa) by Cyclisation of (VI).—The preceding oil (10 g.) was added to polyphosphoric acid (prepared from 50 g. of P₂O₅ and 30 ml of orthophosphoric acid), heated to 70°. The mixture was vigorously stirred whereby the temperature spontaneously rose to 110°, which was brought down to 80-90° for 10 min. and then cooled to the room temperature. Ice-water (200 ml) was added to decompose the polyphosphoric acid when the cyclised product separated as a dark solid (5 g.). After three crystallisations from ethanol, the pure compound was obtained as yellow shining needles, m.p. 217-18°; it did not depress m.p. of the sample (IIIa), prepared by the Gramine route.

5-Nitro-7-methyltryptophan (Vb) was prepared in the same way as for (Va); 1 g. of (IIIb) afforded 0.5 g. of (Vb), m.p. 274-75°. It gave positive test with ninhydrin. (Found: C, 54.36; H, 5.40; N, 16.42. $C_{12}H_{13}O_4N_3$ requires C, 54.75; H, 4.98; N, 15.96%.)

N-Acetyl-5-methoxy-7-nitrotryptophan (IVc).—Compound (IIIc) was heated under reflux for 1½ hr. with a 10% NaOH solution (10 ml.), filtered, and acidified with HCl to obtain α-acetamido-α-carboxy-β-(5-methoxy-7-nitro-3-indolyl)propionic acid, m.p. 175-76° (decomp.), yield 0.75 g. It was then heated under reflux with water (10 ml) until a clear solution resulted from which after cooling and addition of a few drops of HCl (IVc) crystallised. It was recrystallised from hot water as orange microscopic needles, m.p. 227-28°, yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 52.55; H, 5.02; N, 13.52. $C_{14}H_{15}O_6N_3$ requires C, 52.33; H, 4.71; N, 13.08%.)

2-Methyl-5-nitrophenylhydrazine was prepared according to the procedure followed by Bishler¹⁷ for the preparation of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine; m.p. 157-58°, yield 14 g. from 20 g. of 2-methyl-5-nitroaniline. (Found: C, 50.63; H, 5.62; N, 25.61. $C_7H_9O_2N_3$ requires C, 50.29; H, 5.43; N, 25.14%).

γ -Acetamido- $\gamma\gamma$ -diethoxycarbonyl-*n*-butyraldehyde-2-methyl-5-nitrophenylhydrazone (VII) was prepared according to the procedure followed for (VI); m.p. 148-49°, yield 10 g. from 7.5 g. of 2-methyl-5-nitrophenylhydrazine. (Found: C, 54.35; H, 6.46; N, 13.60. $C_{19}H_{26}O_7N_4$ requires C, 54.02; H, 6.20; N, 13.26%).

Attempted Cyclisation of (VII).—Attempts were made to cyclise (VII) as per the procedure followed for the cyclisation of (VI), but only dark coloured sticky mass was obtained which refused crystallisation.

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